

Natural Fiber Reinforced Biocomposites: Effect of Fiber Treatments by Ultrasound

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ABSTRACT

In this study composites were produced using extrusion followed by injection molding of oil palm empty fruit bunch (EFB) fibers with poly(lactic acid). The fiber content was optimized. The optimized EFB fibers were subjected in ultrasound with water and in alkali solution with and without ultrasound treatment. Raw oil palm empty fruit bunch (REFB), alkali treated EFB (AEFB), ultrasound treated EFB (UEFB) and simultaneous ultrasound-alkali treated EFB (UAEFB) short fibers were incorporated in poly(lactic acid) (PLA) for fabricating biocomposites. The alkali solution concentration, soaking time and treatment temperature for treating EFB fibers were 3 wt%, 60 min and 80°C, respectively. Then, raw EFB fibers-PLA (REPC), AEFB fibers-PLA (AEPC), UEFB fibers-PLA (UEPC) and UAEFB fibers-PLA composites (UAEPC) were prepared and characterized. The observed increase in glass transition temperature, crystal melting temperature, decomposition temperature and mechanical properties as well as decrease in crystallization temperature of UAEPC, AEPC and UEPC from REPC has been explained by the increase in crystallinity and interfacial adhesion between treated fibers and PLA. Among all samples, UAEPC shows better performances than other samples. Scanning electron microscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimetry analysis well support all the observed results.

1. INTRODUCTION

Biocomposites which are composed of natural fiber (such as Jute, Kenaf, Hemp, EFB etc.) and polymer have captured significant research interest owing to

their advantages like light-weight, low-cost, availability, reproducibility, biodegradability and environmentally friendly characteristics over glass/carbon fibers, natural fibers have attracted increased attentions as suitable reinforcements in petroleum-based thermoplastics [1]. The reinforced thermoplastics are used as potential composite materials for applications in automotive, construction and building industries [2]. Despite huge markets of petroleum based thermoplastic composites, researchers are trying to reduce the consumption of feedstock energy and seek the alternative renewable resources for fabricating composite materials considering the clean environment. To alleviate the use of fossil-fuel derived thermoplastics, bio-based plastic like poly(lactic acid) (PLA), due to its ease of processes ability and eco-friendly behavior, has emerged as a promising candidate in composite manufacturing [3]. On the other hand, oil palm empty fruit bunch (EFB) fiber among other natural fibers is a readily obtainable fiber in some countries in the world, wasted in the premise of palm oil industries [4]. This trash of EFB fiber is polluting the environment and makes a threat to the human life. If these EFB fibers can be used in reinforcing bioplastics, their disposable problem not only can be resolved but also their use can be extended.

It is notable that the application of PLA is restricted due to its relatively low toughness [5], which needs to be improved for its wider applications. Material toughness is generally related to its crystallinity that can be changed by incorporating nucleating agents into it [6]. In this respect, EFB fiber can play an important role, because both PLA and EFB fibers have the affinity to make hydrogen/covalent bonds after melt processing [7, 8] and this tendency can induce the crystallinity in PLA more than other nucleating agents. However, the inherent drawbacks

of EFB fibers, such as high moisture absorption, low thermal stability and poor incompatibility with polymer matrix, can adversely affect the interaction between the fiber and PLA [7]. To overcome these limitations, alkaline treatment, heat treatment, acetylation, coupling agent treatment, etc. of fibers were proposed [9]. Of these techniques, alkali treatment is a practical approach, leading to the increase in the availability of reactive hydroxyl groups (–OH) on the fiber surface for chemical bonding [10]. A notable other method, not frequently employed for modifying EFB fiber surface, is the ultrasound treatment [8], which can also increase the free –OH groups on fiber surface. Using the ultrasonic method, a few natural fibers other than EFB fiber have been treated to reinforce PLA [8, 11, 12], while published works on alkali treated natural fibers for composites are plenty. Therefore, we have been emphasized to develop methods by using the ultrasonic treatment under both water and alkaline medium for modifying EFB fibers in order to compare its effectiveness in exposing –OH groups on the fiber surface. Through this way, we expect EFB fibers to make more compatible with PLA. In the present study, we will report the enhancement of compatibility between EFB fibers and PLA by differently treated fibers and examine the effect on mechanical, thermal, morphological, structural and crystalline properties of PLA by them, as revealed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) study.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

PLA thermoplastic was collected from Nature Works® PLA, 2002D, USA. Oil palm EFB fibers were obtained from FELDA Palm Oil Refinery, Pahang, Malaysia. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and acetic acid were purchased from Merck, Germany.

2.2 Fibers treatment and composites fabrication

Raw EFB fibers contained several impurities such as sand, mud, palm fruit, palm seed, seed grains, seed shell etc., which were washed out with water-flow. The washed EFB fibers were dried under sun light and then chopped into short fiber in random size of 5–10 mm. During composites fabrication, 10, 20, 30, and 40 wt% fibers were extruded with PLA by a

twin screw extruder (Thermo Scientific Prism Eurolab-16, Germany) at 190°C temperature. The extrudates were pelletized and dried at 80°C for overnight. Tests samples were prepared by injection molding machine of Germany, BOY15-S, with 190°C processing temperature. The maximum values of mechanical properties were obtained for composites considered as the optimum fiber contents in the present study.

These optimized EFB fibers were separately subjected to treatments in alkali medium and by ultrasound in both water and alkali medium using a Daihan Ultrasonic bath. The fiber treatments were conducted at 3 wt% NaOH solution, 60 minutes exposure time and 80°C treatment temperatures with and without ultrasound, maintaining a weight ratio for EFB fiber to solution of 1:10. After completing treatments, fibers were washed thoroughly with water-flow to remove alkali solution from the fiber surface and subsequently neutralized to p^H 7 with a few drops of acetic acid solution and then dried in an oven. Four types of EFB fibers used in this study were raw EFB (REFB), alkali-treated EFB (AEFB), ultrasound-treated EFB (UEFB) and simultaneous ultrasound-alkali treated EFB (UAEFB) fibers. Then, REFB, AEFB, UEFB and UAEFB fibers were first extrusion molded and then injection molded with PLA at 190°C to prepare the final composites, such as REPC, AEPC, UEPC and UAEPC respectively.

2.3 Tensile testing of composites

Tensile testing of composites was carried out in accordance with ASTM 638-08, using a Shimadzu (Model: AG-1) Universal tensile testing machine built-in a 5 kN load cell operated at a cross-head speed of 10 mm/min. Five replicates were evaluated for each type of samples for tensile strength (*TS*) and tensile modulus (*TM*) measurements, keeping 65 mm as the gauge length.

2.4 Impact testing

Impact testing was carried out according to the EN ISO 179 standard by a Ray-Ran Pendulum Charpy Impact System. The impact velocity was 2.9 m/s and the hammer weight was 0.475 kg for this test. Dimensions of the samples were 80 mm × 8 mm × 3.5 mm with a single notch of 0.25 mm. Five replicates were evaluated for each type of samples to obtain the impact strength (*IS*).

2.5 Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy

Chemical textures of composites with untreated and treated fibers were detected by a Nicolet 6700 FT-IR spectrometer, Thermo Scientific, Germany. Fourier transformation infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was performed using the standard KBr pellet technique in the wave number range of 4000–500 cm^{-1} .

2.6 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Fractured surface morphologies of PLA composites with treated and untreated EFB fibers were investigated by using a scanning electron microscope (ZEISS, EVO50, Germany). Samples were mounted on aluminium stubs with carbon tape and then sputter coated with platinum to make them conductive prior to scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2.7 Differential scanning calorimetry

Glass transition temperature (T_g), melting temperature (T_m) and crystallization temperature (T_c) were monitored by the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using a TA/Q1000 apparatus under nitrogen atmosphere. In order to avoid moisture effect, all the test specimens were dried at 90°C for 7 h prior to the measurements. For DSC measurements, the samples were initially heated at temperatures in the range of 30–250°C with a heating rate of 10°C min^{-1} , then cooled down to 30°C with a cooling rate of 5°C min^{-1} and re-heated from 30 to 250°C to monitor calorimetric properties. The degree of DSC crystallinity (X_{dsc}) of the samples was calculated by the heat of fusion for the tested sample and a reference sample with 100% crystallinity using the following relation

$$[14]: X_{dsc} = \left(\frac{\Delta H}{\Delta H_m W} \right) \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

where ΔH is the heat of fusion of the sample under study, ΔH_m of value 93.6 J g^{-1} represents the heat of fusion for 100% crystalline PLA and W is the mass fraction of the matrix [12].

2.8 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric measurements were conducted by a TGA Q500 V6.4, Germany in a platinum

sample pan under nitrogen atmosphere (flow rate 60 ml/min) with a heating rate of 20°C/min. The temperature range was scanned from 25 to 600°C.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Fiber Optimization

Fig. 1 represents the variation of TS and TM with respect to REFB fibers content, where the 30 wt% EFB fibers reinforced PLA composite exhibits the highest mechanical performances among all others. Having optimized fiber content in the composites, these fibers were subjected to treatments in 3wt % alkali solutions at 60 minutes exposure time and 80°C treatment temperatures with and without ultrasound.

3.2 FTIR structural analyses

Fig. 2 illustrates the FTIR spectra of various composites. Visible differences among the investigated spectra of different composites are marked with arrows and dotted enclosures. The differences in the spectra inside the rectangular enclosure in the range 3300–3600 cm^{-1} gives an indication of the degree of hydrogen bond formation between the OH groups of fibers and the C=O or COOH groups of PLA. Evidence on esterification among OH groups of EFB fibers and terminal COOH groups of PLA is the intensity changes at 1756 cm^{-1} peak (arrows) [15].

Supplementary significant differences regarding adhesion between fiber and PLA are the spectral changes in the range 1000–1300 cm^{-1} . These indicate that a fairly large number of available OH groups are exposed on the fiber surface after the alkali, ultrasound and ultrasound-alkali treatments. Conversely, a very limited number of the surface OH groups of untreated fibers takes part in bonding with the C=O and –COOH groups of PLA, as they are mostly engaged with impurities like lignin, pectin etc. Thus, the increased exposure of the OH groups of fibers provides improved potential for hydrogen and covalent bonds formation with C=O and COOH groups of PLA, respectively. We can, therefore, suggest an improved compatibility between treated EFB fibers and matrix, where the effect of ultrasound for fiber-treatment is noticeable.

3.3 Surface morphology

SEM micrographs of the fractured surface of composites are presented in Fig.3, wherein holes, fiber pull-out, fiber-fracture and PLA crystallites are marked. REPC surface seems to show fiber pulled out from the PLA matrix with the creation of noticeable large holes. These could be due to either free volumes developed in REPC or poor adhesion between REFB fibers and PLA.

The poor adhesion is a result of the presence of impurities in the surface of untreated fibers. On the other hand the SEM micrographs of AEPC, UEPC and UAEPC show fiber-fracture and less holes, rather than fiber pull-out. Fiber fracture and fiber pull-out are indicators of the degree of stress transfer from the matrix to the fiber. The presence of fiber fracture and few holes in SEM micrographs of AEPC and UAEPC signify efficient stress transfer from the matrix when the load is applied. Thus, the SEM observations disclose a relatively poor interfacial adhesion in the REPC as compared to composites of the treated fibers. This improved adhesion of treated fibers with PLA may suggest the formation of hydrogen and covalent bonding in composites as discussed earlier.

3.4 Glass transition, crystallization and melting temperatures

DSC thermograms obtained from the 2nd heating course are shown in Fig. 4. The pure PLA has been reported to display glass transition, cold crystallization and melting, which are characterized by temperatures T_g , T_c and T_m , respectively [18]. In this study, the composites show three distinct peaks, including the T_g and the T_c as well as the double melting (T_{m1} and T_{m2}), where T_{m1} and T_{m2} are temperature of low and high temperature endotherms, respectively.

The T_g , T_c , T_m , and $X_{dsc}(\%)$ values evaluated from the DSC runs are summarized in Table 1, showing different values for different samples. The observed T_g value in this study gradually increases based on fibers treatments according to the order UAEPC > UEPC > AEPC > REPC. Most often, it is a common trend to show a low T_g by a sample with a low degree of crystallinity, where the molecules can move easily. The more orderly crystalline state has the higher density, and consequently the non-crystalline molecular chains become inhibited as they are anchored to the immobile crystallites. On the other hand, the increase in crystallinity in PLA has been demonstrated by the incorporation of

nucleating agent, because this nature lowers the surface free energy barrier for nucleation that enables its crystallization at lower temperature on heating [19]. If we compare the degree of recrystallization in composites, REPC shows the highest T_c value (119°C) and UAEPC shows the lowest value (101°C). The lower T_c in composites suggests that treated EFB fibers are more favorable nucleating agents for PLA crystallization during heating.

The early crystallization of PLA by differently treated fibers is probably facilitated by the improved hydrogen and covalent bonding between treated fibers and PLA. As far we know that these effects of differently treated EFB fibers in PLA crystallization have not been published before in any other article. Considering crystal melting, it was suggested that that T_{m1} is originated from small and imperfect crystals, which changed successively into more stable crystals through the melting and recrystallization and an exotherm between the two endothermic peaks is associated to recrystallization [20]. However, more detailed definitions have been given by Pan *et. al.*, who described that T_{m1} is associated with both the phase transition and the melting of the original α -phase crystals, while T_{m2} arises from the α -phase formed during the phase transition and melt-recrystallization [21]. Other explanations have been the existence of either dual crystal structures in a polymer or dual lamellae population in the same crystalline structure of a polymer [22]. To distinguish the effect of differently treated fibers on crystallization in PLA, we invoke the free energy concept for the formation of a nucleus of a critical size [23]:

$$\Delta G^* = \frac{4b\sigma_e T_m^0}{\Delta H_m^0 \Delta T} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Obviously, G^* increases with the decrease of ΔT . Using our DSC data for evaluation of ΔT , we can infer that G^* is the lowest for UAEPC followed by UEPC and AEPC. These results confirm that the energy barrier for nucleation in PLA is lowered treated fibers, leading to an increase in the overall crystallization in PLA. Thus, we suggest that the higher crystallization in biocomposites is due to the increased hydrogen/covalent interactions between matrix and treated fibers.

3.5 Mechanical Properties

The T_S and T_M of the composites are plotted in Fig. 5. The T_S and T_M values are found to gradually increase with incorporation of treated EFB fibers. These results indicate that simultaneous ultrasound-alkali treatment of the EFB fibers facilitates improvement in their mechanical performances. The structures and properties of these samples are subsequently compared with those of REPC and UAEP. The trend of T_S and T_M changes for all these samples investigated here. The trend of I_S changes are shown in Fig. 6, similar to the trend of T_S and T_M changing. The increasing trend in T_S , T_M and I_S of composites are according to the following order: UAEP>UEPC>AEPC>REPC. These observations signify a moderate enhancement in mechanical properties of prepared composite materials by simultaneous ultrasound-alkali treatment of EFB fibers. This enhancement in properties is due to the modification of fiber surface by different treatments and increased compatibility between EFB fibers and PLA, as demonstrated by FTIR, SEM and DSC studies.

3.6 Thermal degradation

Fig.7 illustrates the thermal degradation of the composites investigated in a temperature range of 50–600°C. TGA generally involves the release of absorbed water (if any) from a sample, the “onset” of degradation of molecules in the sample, the steps of degradation and the presence of residual char. The degradation in REPC composite begin at relatively lower temperature than that found in treated EFB incorporated composites such as AEPC, UEPC and UAEP. The TGA traces of composites seem to fall at 100°C, indicating the emission of absorbed moisture. Besides, the TGA sharp-fall, which occurs at 275°C for REPC look quite distinct from that for AEPC, UEPC, UAEP, showing a two-step process in the temperature ranges of 275-380°C and 380-519°C. This may be connected to the decomposition behavior of the molecules of EFB fibers in the differently treated composites. The degradation of natural fiber has been ascribed by the dissociation of C–C chain bonds along with H–abstraction at the site of dissociation [1].

Although, degradation temperature (T_d) can be obtained from TGA traces, it is a common practice to consider the T_d at 50% weight loss of a sample as an indicator for the structural destabilization [23,24]. The T_d values thus evaluated for REPC, AEPC, UEPC, and UAEP from TGA curves are introduced in Table 1.

increase with incorporation of treated EFB fibers.

4. Conclusions

Short EFB fibers have been treated in alkali medium and by ultrasound in water and alkali media and to reinforce PLA for preparing REPC, AEPC, UEPC and UAEP. The reinforced composites, such as UAEP, UEPC and AEPC show an increase in glass transition and crystal melting temperatures as well as a decrease in crystallization temperature as compared to REPC. They also show an increase in mechanical properties from REPC. These superior properties in treated fiber based composites have been explained by the changes in crystallinity and crystalline morphologies in PLA as well hydrogen/covalent bonding between fiber and PLA. FTIR has provided strong evidence of adhesion between them. Information on crystalline structure of the composites as observed by DSC has been found to be consistent. Among various treatments, fibers treated by ultrasound in alkali medium have been found to be more effective than others.

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Fig.1. Variations of *TS* and *TM* as a function of EFB content for the raw composites

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (a) REPC, (b) AEPC, (c) UEPC and (d) UAEPC.

Fig.3.SEM micrographs of (a)REPC, (b)AEPC, (c) UEPC and (d) UAEPC.

Fig.4.DSC thermograms of (a) REPC, (b) AEPC,(c)UEPC and (d) UAEPC from the 2nd heating run.

Fig.5. Tensile strength and tensile modulus of composites.

Fig.6. Impact strength of composites.

Fig.7. TG thermograms of (a) REPC, (b) AEPC, (c) UEPC and (d) UAEPC.

Table 1: The T_g , T_c , T_m , $X_{dsc}(\%)$ and T_d for different samples.

Sample	Thermal properties					
	T_g (°C)	T_c (°C)	T_{m1} (°C)	T_{m2} (°C)	X_{dsc} (%)	T_d (°C)
REPC	56.5	119	140.1	146.6	31	324
AEPC	59.9	108	143.6	150.8	35	332
UEPC	60.6	105	143.6	151.9	41	346
UAEPC	62.2	101	143.6	151.9	43	364